

Optical properties and upconversion in Pr³⁺ doped in aluminium, barium, calcium fluoride glass-II

Anita Rai^a and Vineet Kumar Rai^{b*}

^aDepartment of Chemistry, Jagatpur P.G. College, Varanasi, India

^bPhysics Department, Banaras Hindu University, Varanasi-221 005, India

E-mail : vineetkrrai@yahoo.co.in Fax : 91-542-2368468

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The absorption and the fluorescence spectra of Pr³⁺ ion doped in aluminium, barium, calcium fluoride (ABCF) glass have been studied. Judd-Ofelt theory has been used to derive the optical parameters viz. the oscillator strength, transition probability, branching ratio, stimulated emission cross-section etc. We have also calculated nephelauxetic effect, covalency and bonding parameters for Pr³⁺ in the present lattice. A broad band upconversion has been observed at different wavelengths throughout the visible region when pumped with 810 nm radiation from a Ti-Sapphire laser.

Triply ionized Pr³⁺ doped in glasses/crystals is known to give strong fluorescence in blue, green, orange and red regions when pumped with light source of suitable wavelength. Due to this Pr³⁺ doped compounds are often used as phosphors. The optical properties of Pr³⁺ in various types of glasses as well as in crystals have been studied by several workers¹.

In this paper we report our studies on the optical properties of Pr³⁺ doped in aluminium-barium-calcium fluoride (ABCF) glass. The absorption and fluorescence spectra of these glasses have been measured and Judd-Ofelt theory has been used to explain the experimental observations. The optical parameters of Pr³⁺ in ABCF glass has been determined using absorption and fluorescence data. Broad band upconversion has been observed at several wavelengths in Pr³⁺ when pumped with 810 nm radiation from a Ti-Sapphire laser.

Experimental

ABC Fluoride glass has been prepared by mixing 30 mol% AlF₃, 15 mol% AlPO₄, 25 mol% BaF₂, 28 mol% CaF₂ and 2 mol% of PrF₃. These compounds were obtained from B.D.H. (India) with 99.0% purity. The rare earth fluoride was obtained from Aldrich chemicals with stated 99.9% purity. These chemicals were mixed in an agate mortar for one hour to ensure a homogeneous mixing. The mixture was then heated in a platinum crucible at 1050°C upto 6 h. During this the melt was stirred continuously to get a homogeneous mixing. The molten mass was then transferred to a cast kept at 200°C. It was kept at this temperature for one hour and then cooled slowly to room tempera-

ture. Several pieces of glass were prepared following the same method. The glasses thus formed were cleaned and polished for further measurements. The density and refractive index of the glass was measured following the method described in an earlier work². The absorption spectrum of the glass was recorded using Cary 2390 (UV-Vis.NIR) spectrophotometer in the 300–3000 nm regions. The fluorescence measurement was carried out at room temperature using 476.5 nm line with 100 mW power from a 10 W Ar⁺ laser. The glass sample was mounted on a blackened metallic stand and the fluorescence emission was recorded at 90° to the incident beam with the help of a 0.5 m Spex mono-

Fig. 1. Fluorescence spectrum of Pr³⁺ doped in ABCF glass.

chromator in the region 500–750 nm. The fluorescence spectrum thus obtained is given in Fig. 1. For upconversion measurements the laser radiation from a Ti-Sapphire laser is focused vertically in the glass kept closed to the slit. A weak orange fluorescence was seen in the glass. The laser wavelengths were tuned to get optimum fluorescence. The

corresponding excitation wavelength of the laser was found to be 810 nm. The visible fluorescence arising due to up-conversion is shown in Fig. 2. The upconversion fluorescence was also monitored by varying the pump power of the laser.

Results and discussion

The electronic configuration of Pr³⁺ ion is 4f² 5s² 5p⁶, which gives 13 electronic states with ³H₄ state to have minimum energy. The absorption spectrum in present case shows nine bands similar to the one observed in other crystals/glasses³ except a small change in intensity and position of the bands. The characteristic bands in the blue region appears with high intensity. Similarly, a broad band is seen in orange red region. The assignments of bands posed no problem. These bands arise due to a transition from ³H₄ to various excited states. The wavelength of the bands along with their assignments are given in Table 1. The bands due to ³P_{0,1,2} ← ³H₄; ¹D₂ ← ³H₄ and ³F₂ ← ³H₄ appear with high intensity. The ¹D₂ ← ³H₄ band is broad whereas others are sharp enough. The oscillator strength of the bands were determined using the relation,

$$F_{exp} = 4.32 \times 10^{-9} \int \epsilon(\nu) d\nu \tag{1}$$

where $\epsilon(\nu)$ is molar absorptivity and is equal to $1/CL \log I_0/I$ from Beer-Lambert law. C represents the concentration of rare earth in the glass and L is its optical path length. $\log I_0/I$ is called optical density. The F_{exp} thus obtained are given in Table 1.

Fig. 2. Upconversion luminescence for Pr³⁺ doped in ABCF glass.

According to Judd-Ofelt theory⁴ the oscillator strength can be written as,

$$F_{cal} = \nu \sum_{\lambda=2,4,6} T(\lambda) (\Psi_{J||U^{\lambda}||\Psi'_{J'})^2 \tag{2}$$

where ν is the absorption frequency; $\zeta(\lambda)$ is related with Judd-Ofelt intensity parameter as

$$\Omega_{\lambda} = \frac{3h(2J+1)T(\lambda)}{8\pi^2 mc\chi} \tag{3}$$

Here $\chi = \frac{(n^2 + 2)^2}{9n}$, n being the refractive index of the glass.

The theoretical values of oscillator strength thus obtained are compared with the experimental values in Table 1. The Judd-Ofelt intensity parameters are also given in the same table. These values follow the trend $\Omega_4 > \Omega_6 > \Omega_2$ which is generally observed in fluoride (ionic lattice) glasses.

Table 1. Assignments of the peaks observed in the absorption spectrum of Pr³⁺ doped ABCF glass (from ground state ³H₄) and the oscillator strength of different transition

Energy levels	Free ion (nm)	ABCF Glass (nm)	$F_{exp} \times 10^6$	$F_{cal} \times 10^6$
³ P ₂	432	450	5.12	6.5
³ P ₁	454	472	1.92	1.58
³ P ₀	468	483	2.81	2.92
¹ D ₂	577	586	2.18	1.95
¹ G ₄	1008	1014	1.32	1.39
³ F ₄	1459	1469	1.83	2.61
³ F ₃	1559	1563	4.32	5.21
³ F ₂	1930	1932	0.92	1.00
³ H ₆	2001	2005	0.31	0.36

$\Omega_2 = 1.15 \times 10^{-20} \text{ cm}^{-2}$, $\Omega_4 = 6.36 \times 10^{-20} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ and $\Omega_6 = 2.82 \times 10^{-20} \text{ cm}^{-2}$.

Fig. 3. $\log I$ versus $\log P$ plot for upconversion luminescence observed in Pr³⁺ doped in ABCF glass.

A general feature in the spectra of lanthanides is an absorption band shift towards lower energy on complex formation called nephelauxetic effect. The nephelauxetic effect $\bar{\beta}$ is approximated as

$$\bar{\beta} = (1/n) [\Sigma (\nu_{complex}/\nu_{free ion})] \tag{4}$$

This permits one to calculate covalency and bonding parameters (δ) and ($b^{1/2}$) respectively using the known relations

$$\delta = (1 - \bar{\beta})/\bar{\beta} \tag{5}$$

$$b^{1/2} = [(1 - \bar{\beta})/2]^{1/2} \tag{6}$$

In the present case these values were found to be 0.984, 1.626 and 0.089 respectively.

Table 2. Fluorescence bands, wavelength, effective bandwidth and the stimulated emission cross section for Pr³⁺ doped ABCF glass

Transition	λ (nm)	Frequency of the bands (cm ⁻¹)	$\Delta\lambda$ (nm)	$\sigma_{sp}^E \times 10^{21}$ cm ²
³ P ₁ → ³ H ₅	525	19047.6	8.1	30.2
³ P ₀ → ³ H ₅	540	18518.5	4.5	-
¹ D ₂ → ³ H ₄	603	16583.7	10.6	44.6
³ P ₀ → ³ H ₆	610	16393.4	12.8	48.8
³ P ₀ → ³ F ₂	642	15576.3	7.5	28.5
³ P ₁ → ³ F ₃	678	14749.3	-	-
³ P ₀ → ³ F ₄	730	13698.6	-	-

The fluorescence spectrum of the glass shows large number of peaks (8 peaks) in the 500–750 nm region (Fig. 1). The peak near 600 nm is broad and very intense and appears to arise due to superposition of two bands. An energy consideration reveals that it is due to ³P₀ → ³H₆ and ¹D₂ → ³H₄ transitions. Another intense band due to ³P₀ → ³F₂ transition appears near 645 nm. A third intense band appears near 527 nm due to ³P₁ → ³H₅ transition. The energies of the bands and their assignments are given in Table 2. The spontaneous emission probability for the electric dipole allowed transitions is given as,

$$A(\Psi'_{J'} \rightarrow \Psi_J) = \frac{64\pi^4 v^3 n(n^2 + 2)^2 e^2}{3hc^3 (2J + 1) 9} S_{ed} \quad (7)$$

where e is the electronic charge, h is Planck constant and c is the velocity of light. S_{ed} is the electric dipole line strength. Its value is given as,

$$S_{ed}(S, L, J; S', L', J') = \sum_{\lambda=2,4,6} \Omega_{\lambda} |\langle S, L, J || U^{\lambda} || S', L', J' \rangle|^2 \quad (8)$$

The total transition probability A_T

$$A_T(\Psi'_{J'}) = \sum A(\Psi'_{J'} \rightarrow \Psi_J) \quad (9)$$

The radiative lifetime τ_r of the fluorescent level is defined as

$$\tau_r = 1/\sum A \quad (10)$$

The fluorescence branching ratio $\beta_r(\Psi'_{J'})$ have been calculated using the relation

$$\beta_r(\Psi'_{J'}) = A(\Psi'_{J'} \rightarrow \Psi_J) / A_T(\Psi'_{J'}) \quad (11)$$

Similarly, the stimulated emission cross section of the fluorescing level have been calculated using the relation

$$\sigma_{sp}^E = \frac{\lambda^4}{8\pi^2 c n^2 \Delta\lambda} \cdot A(\Psi'_{J'} \rightarrow \Psi_J) \quad (12)$$

where λ is the wavelength of the peak and $\Delta\lambda$ is the effective bandwidth. The effective bandwidth is obtained by dividing the integrated intensity of the band by the intensity at the peak of the band. All these values are given in Table 3.

Table 3. Radiative transition probability and branching ratio for the ³P₁, ³P₀ and ¹D₂ levels for Pr³⁺ doped in ABCF glass

Levels	³ P ₁		³ P ₀		¹ D ₂	
	A	β_r	A	β_r	A	β_r
³ P ₁	-	-	-	-	-	-
³ P ₀	-	-	-	-	-	-
¹ D ₂	162	0.006	40	0.001	-	-
¹ G ₄	27	0.001	67	0.002	150	0.043
³ F ₄	82	0.002	240	0.007	420	0.122
³ F ₃	11463	0.413	-	-	115	0.033
³ F ₂	5490	0.197	15048	0.454	630	0.184
³ H ₆	100	0.004	2930	0.088	750	0.219
³ H ₅	10280	0.370	-	-	30	0.008
³ H ₄	125	0.004	14810	0.447	1320	0.386
Radiative lifetime (τ_r)	36.0 μ s		30.1 μ s		292.8 μ s	

Table 4. Wavelength of the upconversion bands and their assignments

Wavelength (nm)	Assignments
451	³ P ₂ → ³ H ₄
475	³ P ₁ → ³ H ₄
486	³ P ₀ → ³ H ₄
526	³ P ₁ → ³ H ₅
557	³ P ₀ → ³ H ₅
597	¹ D ₂ → ³ H ₄
616	³ P ₀ → ³ H ₆
641	³ P ₀ → ³ F ₂
676	³ P ₁ → ³ F ₃
731	³ P ₀ → ³ F ₄

Fig. 4. The energy level diagram for upconversion in Pr³⁺ doped in ABCF glass.

Upconversion excitation :

Upconversion emission at different wavelengths through out the visible region have been observed in Pr³⁺ doped ABCF glass when pumped with NIR radiation at 810 nm. Upconversion in UV region has also been observed in Pr³⁺ doped fluoride glass when pumped with blue or yellow light. The NIR to visible upconversion in Pr³⁺ doped in ABCF glass on excitation with 810 nm radiation from a Ti-Sapphire laser is shown in Fig. 2 and the wavelength of the upconversion bands are given in Table 4. Upconversions are observed for nearly all bands for which one photon fluorescence is seen. The three peaks observed in blue green region due to well known $^3P_2 \rightarrow ^3H_4$, $^3P_1 \rightarrow ^3H_4$, $^3P_0 \rightarrow ^3H_4$ transitions. The peaks observed in orange-red region are due to $^1D_2 \rightarrow ^3H_4$ and $^3P_0 \rightarrow ^3H_6$ transition as also observed in fluorescence spectrum. Normally, upconversion is not observed from 3P_2 level in Pr³⁺ doped other host materials but in our case we get the upconversion from 3P_2 level due to $^3P_2 \rightarrow ^3H_4$ transition. Similarly, one sharp upconversion peak observed near 641 nm is due to $^3P_0 \rightarrow ^3F_2$. Weak upconversion is also observed at 676 and 731 nm and they are due to $^3P_1 \rightarrow ^3F_3$ and $^3P_0 \rightarrow ^3F_4$ transitions. Thus using a NIR radiation one can get upconversion emission through out the visible region.

The appearance of upconversion in visible region on pumping with NIR is obviously a two/three photon process. To be sure about this we measured the intensity of $^3P_0 \rightarrow ^3F_2$ and $^3P_1 \rightarrow ^3H_4$ peaks for different NIR pump power. The slope of $\log I$ versus $\log P$ gives a value 1.93 and 1.89 in the two cases (as shown in Fig. 3) indicating clearly that two-photon absorption are involved in both the upconversion process. The upconversion luminescence arises mostly by one of the two mechanisms.

(i) Excited state absorption (ESA) and

(ii) Energy transfer upconversion (ETU).

The energy level diagram of Pr³⁺ is shown in Fig. 4. In present case the upconversion is observed on pumping with 810 nm ($\sim 12300 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) radiation. The Pr³⁺ ion on absorption of $\sim 12300 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ radiation is promoted to 1G_4 level (through phonon assisted excitation). Since we observe upconversion transition from 3P_J levels, it is possible only when excited Pr³⁺ ion in the 1G_4 level reabsorb the incident photon of the energy $\sim 12300 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ (i.e. the ESA process). Energy transfer amongst the excited ions will not be sufficient to populate 3P_J . Therefore, the upconversions ob-

served in blue region are due to excited state absorption (ESA). The 3P_J levels also give upconversion emission in orange and red regions. The 1D_2 level is populated by the relaxation from 3P_J levels. The other possibility of population of 1D_2 level is via ETU i.e.

But in this case the intensity of the upconversion band $^1D_2 \rightarrow ^3H_4$ should be large enough. In the present case $^1D_2 \rightarrow ^3H_4$ transition appears weak. Therefore, the most probable process of 1D_2 level population is via relaxation from 3P_J levels.

Conclusion :

The absorption and fluorescence spectra of Pr³⁺ doped in aluminium, barium, calcium fluoride glass have been studied and optical properties viz. the oscillator strength, transition probability, total transition probability, branching ratio, stimulated emission cross section etc. have been obtained. The nephelauxetic parameters representing the effect of host on the energy levels of the ion have also been studied. Broad band upconversion emissions covering nearly the whole visible region have been observed on excitation with 810 nm NIR radiation. A plot of laser power versus emitted intensity of the upconverted signals indicates that they are due to two-photon absorption. The mechanism involved in the process is excited state absorption (ESA).

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